

DIGITAL SOLUTIONS FOR THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract: The next article will focus on the developing forms of education in the system of preschool, secondary and higher education in our country, which in many cases can replace traditional teaching methods. This is due to the fact that it uses the most modern technologies, including video, mobile devices and social networks, as a tool for high-quality learning needed by the student, students.

Keywords: Education, digital technologies, Preschool education, secondary education, oily education, information and communication technologies.

INTRODUCTION

Digital technologies are so ingrained in our lives that today it is impossible to imagine without them not only our daily activities, but also the development of socio-economic spheres. Naturally, the introduction of digital technologies into the national education system of our country, as in other areas, will lay the foundation for a radical change in its functioning.

To the question of What digital technology itself is, we will answer this way: it is a modern form of management. in it, the main factor of production and management is a large set of data in digital form and the process of their processing. And the application of the results obtained in practice makes it possible to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of management. Examples include various automated production processes, 3D

technologies, cloud technologies. provision of remote medical services, production and delivery of products using intelligent technologies, storage and sale of various goods. Currently, in the era of globalization, innovative educational technologies and their pedagogical foundations are being studied, one of the urgent problems of today remains the study of ways to effectively use modern interactive teaching methods in the educational process. The socio-pedagogical necessity of an innovative approach to education is measured:

1. Scientific and technological progress and socio-economic renewal of the system of continuing education, in particular, the improvement of the educational process in educational institutions using advanced foreign experience, innovative approaches in education and information technology;

2. Creation and implementation in practice of effective organizational forms, technologies of personality-oriented learning, serving the development of the level of education, intellectual potential, social activity, creative skills among the young people studying;

3. The need to develop professional and innovative competence of a teacher in relation to the development of pedagogical innovations and their implementation.

Scientific observations and studies have shown that seventy percent of all the information that a person receives during his life, he manages to get at the age of five. One of the most important and urgent tasks is the introduction into the educational process of modern educational programs, advanced information and pedagogical technologies that provide comprehensive intellectual, spiritual, moral and physical development of children, improving their level of preparation for school, creating modern standards of preschool education management. Systemic changes in the socio-economic, spiritual and moral, information and communication and educational systems of our republic are seriously changing human life. In such an honorable and responsible matter as the upbringing of a well-rounded personality in an independent country, an important place is

occupied by the system of preschool education, which is the initial link of the education system. Starting from the moment of birth of a child, it is at preschool age that his mental activity increases, moral aesthetic and physical sensations are formed. Therefore, our strategic goal for the development of preschool education in the coming years is to create the necessary conditions for the full coverage of this area of education for every child of preschool age, regardless of social status. Such updates require the rapid introduction of pedagogical innovations in the field of education and the system of continuing education. —Innovative work is a Latin word meaning renewal, innovation, - innovative work. Innovation involves the creation of new ideas that serve to improve the form and content of the educational process. Innovative ideas are rapidly penetrating into today's educational practice. Pedagogical innovations serve to improve the quality and effectiveness of education, any processes of renewal in society, reforms are inextricably linked with the essence. The development of preschool children, the establishment of requirements for the content and quality of education, the importance of innovative and information and communication technologies in the educational process are among the most important tasks of the state standard of preschool education and upbringing. Based on such tasks, the choice of the most modern, age-appropriate means for the educational process requires the knowledge and experience of teaching staff. On the other hand, the role of teachers is important for the education and development of the child. Because in preschool educational organizations, the educator is the teacher, and the children are the recipient. When implementing such tasks, a preschool educational organization requires its experienced teachers to be able to effectively use innovative and information and communication technologies in the learning process, to have knowledge. It cannot be denied that at present the improvement of the education system is directly related to the degree of effective implementation of modern innovative and information and communication technologies in practice. Pedagogical technology is an innovative approach to the

educational process.

It is important that the digital environment becomes a factor of human development, a means of meaningful filling of the process of moral development of the individual, the formation of the basis and direction of life plans and behavior of the subject. The use of educational robotics in teaching school subjects is one of the innovative tools these days. Robotics is taught as a separate subject in secondary schools in developed countries and a number of competitions are held to develop this field. Especially in Japan, the USA, Germany, South Korea and similar countries, the didactic capabilities of educational robotics are widely used in teaching STEM subjects. In our country, there is no opportunity to take full advantage of the possibilities of educational robotics, since this industry has come recently. That is why the use of visual programming environment is now becoming more and more popular in schools in developed and developing countries, because it is easier to understand than visual programming languages and text programming languages.

Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) it is a broad term used to unify academic disciplines. The term is commonly used in schools to refer to educational policies or curriculum choices. This affects the development of the workforce, national security issues (since a shortage of citizens with STEM education can reduce efficiency in this area) and immigration policy.

In preschool or after entering school, the chances of STEM success in high school can be significantly increased by developing an interest in natural and social sciences. STEM supports the study of engineering in each of the other subjects, the expansion and the beginning of engineering in the lower grades, even in elementary school. It also brings STEAM education to all students, not just the gifted. In his 2012 budget, President Barack Obama changed and expanded the name of the Math and Science Partnership (MSP) to provide block grants to States

to improve teacher training in these subjects. STEM education often uses new technologies such as RepRap 3D printers to stimulate interest in STEM fields.¹

Today's classrooms are very different from those of 10-15 years ago, and classrooms are equipped with computers, tablets, smart boards and other types of educational technologies. The adaptation of the education system to the digital generation through the mass and effective use of innovative educational technologies and didactic models based on modern information and communication technologies is a requirement of the time. The skill of a teacher and the effectiveness of his activity lies not only in the level of knowledge of the content of the subject being taught and his pedagogical abilities, but also in the ways of accumulating, processing and teaching certain educational material and bringing this knowledge to the consciousness of students, depending on how modern information and communication technologies the teacher uses. In other words, in the digital age, education needs to be revised, and the paradigm of education needs to be changed, because students do not want to learn in a more traditional way, and the fact that teachers continue to teach in the same conventional way is denied by today itself. Providing students with education using digital technologies facilitates the student's assimilation of the acquired knowledge. What prevents a student from gaining knowledge? the question arises: "why?" First of all, boredom. Looking around, 204 young people with an ordinary smartphone in their hands remain busy, not knowing how their time has passed. We need to adapt our current educational process to such times so that we can find ways to use pedagogical technologies using this simple smartphone, of course, at the same time, young students will be more and more interested in obtaining the knowledge they are taught.

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/STEM>.

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